

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SELF-CONCEPT BETWEEN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH HEARING AND SPEECH IMPAIRMENTS AND THEIR TYPICALLY DEVELOPING PEERS

Dr. Manisha Jamod

Assistant Professor
Nandkunvarba Mahila College, Bhavnagar
Affiliated to Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study to the changes and awareness in society under the theme of “The role of Psychology in new Horizon for professionals in India”. Self-concept, as the perception each person has of himself or herself, is a component of personality development. The aim of the present study was investigated to self-concept among Deaf & Dumb students and Normal students studying in primary school. The random sampling method was used in this study. The total sample consisted 120 students. 60 of Deaf & Dumb and 60 of Normal students studying in primary school. The sample was selected from Bhavnagar city. The research tool for Children’s self -concept scale developed by Ahluwalia, S.P. (2002). In the research children’s self-concept inventory was used for data collection. Data was analyzed by ‘t’-test verify the hypothesis. The result shows that ‘t’-value is high and that is significant at 0.01 level. So the hypothesis are not accepted. It means there is huge difference between Self-concept among Deaf & Dumb students and Normal students.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of self-concept has awakened growing interest in psychological research of recent years. Despite the profusion of studies devoted to it, it is difficult to definition of the term self – concept, given, that it has been approached from different theoretical perspectives. Nonetheless, there does exist agreement among the different methods in that the term self concept has a multi dimensional nature. Self-concept is considered to comprise various dimensions, areas of facts, some of which are more related to certain personality aspect (physical, social, emotional), while others appear to be more linked to academic achievement (in different areas and subjects).

2. SELF-CONCEPT

Self-concept “is the set of perception or reference prints that the subject has about himself; the set of characteristics, attributes, gratitude’s and deficiencies, capacities and limits, values and relationship that subjects knows to be descriptive of himself and which he perceives as data concerning his identity” (Hamachek, 1981, Quoted by Machurgo, 1991 : 24). It is the set of knowledge and attitudes that we have about ourselves; The perceptions that the individual assigns to himself and characteristics or attributes that we use to describe ourselves. It is understood to be fundamentally a descriptive assessment and has a cognitive nuance.

“A man self is the sum total of all that he can his the notion of appropriation and identity it in to three constituent parts the material me, the social me and the spiritual me.”

William James (1980) “In general person is an all-inclusive term referring to a single living human being as well as all the social and psychological characteristics and possessions we

might attribute to that being it may also be used in amore restricted bodily sense to refer to the physical organism.”

English & English (1958) Some authors, like Herter (1986), make interesting contributions, such as that general or global self concept will be determined by the agree of importance that we assign to each of its specific components. If, when describing ourselves, our value judgments are satisfactory, then we obtain a positive globe self concept, in the opposite case we generate negative feelings and thus produce a negative global self concept.

Every child has the right to educate himself. However we come across children who are physically challenged especially with regards to their hearing ability and speaking ability. Such children should not be deprived education.

3. DEAF AND DUMB STUDENTS

(A). Deaf Students

Students who are deaf or hard of hearing require different accommodation depending on several factors, including the degree of hearing loss. The age of onset, and the type of language or communication system they use. They may use a variety of communication methods, including lip reading, cued speech, signed English and / or American sign language.

Deaf education is the education of students with a variety of hearing levels which address their difference and individually planned, systematically monitored teaching method, adaptive materials, accessible setting and other interventions designed to help students achieve a higher level of self – sufficiency and success in the school and community.

Identifying Deaf Students

Children may be identified as a candidate for deal education from their audiogram or medical history. Hearing loss is generally described as slight, mild, moderate, severe or profound, depending upon how well a person can hear the intensities of frequencies.

(B). Dumb Students

Deaf mate is a term which was used historically to identify a person who was either deaf using a sign language of both deaf and could not speak. The term continues to be used to refer to deaf people who cannot speak and oral language or have some degree of speaking ability, but choose not to speak because of the negative or unwanted attention typical voice sometimes attract. Such people communicate using sign language. Some consider it to be a derogatory term if used outside its historical context the preferred term today is simply “deaf”. The simple identify of ‘Deaf’ has been embraced by the community of signing deaf people since the foundations of public deaf education in the 18th century and remains the preferred term of reference or identity for many years. Within the deaf community there are some who prefer the term ‘Deaf’ to ‘Deaf’ as a description of their status and identity.

4. EDUCATING THE DEAF AND DUMB STUDENTS

Education is important for Deaf and Dumb students for their academic growth as well as for the development of their all round personality. These impaired children lack the ability to use language and communication skills for educational purposes like their normal peers. That’s why: different approaches and methods are employed for teaching.

5. RELATED STUDY

- Parthasurthy & Swaminathen, (1992), “Self concept among normal destitute & Orphan Children.”

- Richard M. Lerner, (2009), “Physical attractiveness, body attitudes and self concept in late adolescents.”
- Kedarnath, (1990), “Self-concept academic achievement and psychological well being.”

6. OBJECTIVE

1. To study about self-concept among Deaf & Dumb and Normal students.
2. To study about self-concept among Deaf & Dumb and Normal Girls.
3. To study about self-concept among Deaf & Dumb and Normal Boys.

7. HYPOTHESIS

1. There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb students and Normal students.
2. There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb and Normal Girls.
3. There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb and Normal Boys.

8. VARIABLE

(A) Independent Variable

1. Types of Student : Deaf & Dumb students / Normal student
2. Gender : Girls / Boys

(B) Dependent Variable

- To get score on self concept among Deaf & Dumb and Normal students.

(C) Controlled Variables:

Control variable of the research is as follow:

1. Same test was given to all students.
2. In this study equal numbers of students were selected from only the Bhavnagar district.

9. SAMPLE

The aim and object of this research is to study of Internet Add

Sample

According to this aims of this study, The sample consisted of 120 primary school students. Out of which 60 of Deaf & Dumb students and 60 of normal students. From each of these 60 students; 30 of Girls and 30 of Boys was selected as a sample in this research. the sample was selected by random method from Bhavnagar City.

10. TOOLS

In this research, self-concept questionnaire where used from the data collection. It was constructed and standardized by Ahluwalia, S.P. (2002). They have made English Version scale but investigator has used Gujarati Version scale made by Yogesh Jogsan. The reliability is 0.83 and the validity was very high.

10.1 Research Design

Primary school students at two level

2 x 2 factorial design

N = 120, n = 30

A1		A2	
Deaf & Dumb Students (60)		Normal Students (60)	
B1	B2	B1	B2
Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
n=30	n=30	n=30	n=30

10.2 Statistical Technique

Here in this study ‘t’-test was used for data interpretation.

10.3 Result and Discussion

1. Self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Students and Normal Students.

The effect of Deaf & Dumb Students and Normal students on their Self concept was examined. The result are presented in the table no – 1.

Table No – 1

Mean, SD and ‘t’ – value of self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Students and Normal Students.

Variable	Sample (N)	Mean	S.D	‘t’	‘t’-value	Level of sig.
Deaf & Dumb students	60	60.12	6.34	8.68	0.01=2.63 0.05=1.98	0.01
Normal Students	60	68.45	3.90			

To study about there is significant difference or not between self concept of Deaf & Dumb Students and Normal Students. , null hypothesis No.1 was constructed.

Ho.1 There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb students and Normal students.

The normal students received higher mean score 68.45 as compared to the deaf & dumb students, the deaf & dumb students mean score of 60.12. There has mean difference was 8.33 and the standard deviation score of normal students received 3.90 and the deaf and dumb students received 6.34. So we can say that normal students have a good self concept than deaf and dumb students, the ‘t’-test value of self concept was 8.68. According to the ‘t’-test the numeric value that we get is 8.68 which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the hypotheses that there will be no significant difference on self concept among deaf and dumb students and normal students is not acceptable. It means there is significant difference in self concept among Deaf & Dumb students, normal students.

Graph No. 1: Chart showing mean scores of self concept with reference to deaf and dumb students and normal students.

2. Self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls.

The effect of Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls on their Self concept was examined. The result are presented in the table no – 2.

Table No – 2

Mean, SD and ‘t’ – value of self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls.

Variable	Sample (N)	Mean	S.D	‘t’	‘t’-value	Level of sig.
Deaf & Dumb Girls	30	63.1	4.07	4.76	0.01=2.63 0.05=1.98	0.01
Normal Girls	30	68.0	3.95			

To study about there is significant difference or not between self concept of Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls. , null hypothesis No.2 was constructed.

Ho.2. There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls.

The normal girls received higher mean score 68.0 as compared to the deaf & dumb girls, the deaf & dumb girls mean score of 63.1. There has mean difference was 4.9 and the standard deviation score of normal girl students received 3.95 and the deaf and dumb girl students received 4.07. So we can say that normal girls have a good self concept than deaf and dumb girls, the ‘t’-test value of self concept was 4.76. According to the ‘t’-test the numeric value that we get is 4.76 which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the hypotheses that there will

be no significant difference on self concept among deaf and dumb girl students and normal girl students is not acceptable.

It means there is significant difference in self concept among Deaf & Dumb girl students, normal girl students.

Graph No. 2: Chart showing mean scores of self concept with reference to deaf and dumb girls and normal girls.

3. Self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys.

The effect of Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys on their Self concept was examined. The result are presented in the table no – 3.

Table No – 3

Mean, SD and ‘t’ – value of self concept with reference to Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys.

Variable	Sample (N)	Mean	S.D	‘t’	‘t’-value	Level of sig.
Deaf & Dumb Boys	30	57.13	6.79	8.29	0.01=2.63	0.01
Normal Boys	30	68.9	3.79		0.05=1.98	

To study about there is significant difference or not between self concept of Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys. , null hypothesis No.3 was constructed.

Ho.3. There will be no significant difference between self concept of Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys.

The normal Boys received higher mean score 68.9 as compared to the deaf & dumb Boys, the deaf & dumb boys mean score of 57.13. There has mean difference was 11.77 and the standard deviation score of normal boys students received 3.79 and the deaf and dumb boys students received 6.79 .So we can say that normal boys have a good self concept than deaf and dumb boys, the ‘t’-test value of self concept was 8.29. According to the ‘t’-test the numeric value that we get is 8.29 which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the hypotheses that there

will be no significant difference on self concept among deaf and dumb boys and normal boys students is not acceptable. It means there is significant difference in self concept among Deaf & Dumb boys students, normal boys students.

Graph No. 3: Chart showing mean scores of self concept with reference to deaf and dumb boys and normal boys.

11. Conclusion

1. There is significant difference of self-concept Deaf & Dumb and Normal students.
2. There is significant difference in self concept between Deaf & Dumb Girls and Normal Girls.
3. There is significant difference in self concept between Deaf & Dumb Boys and Normal Boys.

REFERENCES

1. Aluwalia, S.P. (2002), "Manual for children's self concept scale", Agra National Psychological corporation.
2. Brook Over W.B., Thomas & Paterson A. (1964), "Self concept of ability and school achievement", Sociology of Education.
3. Bhammar M.V. (2009), "A comparative study of self concept, emotional stability and academic achievement motivation among study in Gujarati and English medium children.
4. Francisco Javier Peralta Sanchez Maria Dolores Sanchez Roda, "Relationship between self concept and academic achievement in primary students."
5. O.F. Akinpela, 'A study of the academic achievement and self concept of male and female hearing – impaired students in Nigeria.'
6. R.S. Patel (2009), "Statistical methods for Educational Research", Second edition, Jay Publication, Ahmedabad.